

INDIA'S SOFT POWER: PRESENCE IN LATIN AMERICA AND CARIBBEAN REGION

RAJ MONGIA

Group Captain, PhD student, Amity Institute of Defence and Strategic Studies, Amity University, Noida Campus, NCR, India.

Dr. ANAND KUMAR TEWARI

Brigadier, Director and HOI, Amity Institute of Defence and Strategic Studies, Amity University, Noida Campus, NCR, India.

Abstract:

As an ancient civilization, India has a vibrant democracy, the largest in the world, a secular spirit and a fast-developing marketplace that grew to become the 5th most developing economy in 2019, surpassing the United Kingdom and France. India, to nurture its communication, tourism, culture and soft power, on the whole, will have to mould multilateral and bilateral collaborations with different nations by augmenting its foreign policy and diplomacy. Owing to the attractiveness of India's culture, social values, and foreign policies in addition to the nation's economic and military might, India will be better positioned to join the rank of Asia's great powers. India, which is aspiring to become a superpower by 2025, also possesses soft power advantage having a democratic system juxtaposed to China's communist belligerent system. For the last ten years, India has likewise exhilarated its indispensable resources in public diplomacy, by employment of traditional as well as innovative methods to create and anchorage its soft power. LAC nations are important for India as these nations support Indian position on various international issues.

Keywords: Soft power, Yoga, Bollywood, Ayurveda

INTRODUCTION

India's has long tradition of employing its soft power in relevant matters. Noted ancient Indian scholars like Kautilya and Kamandak have referred to 'Soft' diplomacy, including practice of Sandhi (Treaty) for achieving progress. Role of Doot (Ambassador) in fostering interstate relationships has been stressed time and again by these scholars. Contemporary international community is truly impressed by India's accommodation of the 'other', its plurality, multiculturalism and secularism. India is an ancient country with a rich legacy of vibrant soft power. The sub-continent is definitely aware of the relevance of its cultural engagement and requires going an extra mile to present its culture attractive to the corners of the world. Notion of soft power is synchronous with the abundant history of India as both a country of intellect and thoughts¹ coupled with amicable cultural co-existence. India's soft power brought with it an impression of uprightness which earned the admiration of the developing nations across the world.

India's Pluralism and Wealth

India is characterised by a pluralistic government, non-violent, and liberal with a non-threatening global leadership. Distinguished personalities like Mahatma Gandhi, Rabindranath

Tagore and attributes like literature, music, dance, software industry, Ayurveda, etc., exhibit an array of soft power assets that epitomise the attractiveness of India to the foreign populace².

In ancient times (from 3000 BCE to around 10th century AD) India's astounding wealth and prosperity earned it the sobriquet of being a 'Golden Sparrow'³. This era witnessed many popular dynasties like Maurya, Shunga, Kushan, Gupta, etc. The major reason why India was named 'Golden Sparrow' was because of its abundant raw materials and availability of precious stones. Mauryan ships used to sail as far as Syria, Egypt and Greece. On this ground the ancient India was a global trade centre. Gold was first found in the lands of India. Its GDP, was also more than that of China.

Virtues of the Land: Benevolent approach

Respect, harmony and fraternity are the virtues that Indians are recognized for, with Ashoka, Buddha and Gandhi as principal paragons. Epics such as Mahabharata and Ramayana are often compared with the great Greek writings like Odyssey and Iliad. India's prosperity lured migrants, traders and invaders like 'Alexander' to India. While submitting the Draft Constitution to the President of the Constituent Assembly on 21 February 1948, B R Ambedkar wrote that the drafting committee had added a clause on "fraternity" in the Preamble (even though it was not part of the Objective Resolution). Fraternity translates into **a spirit of brotherhood among the people of the land**. India is a land of immense diversity. Its spirit of brotherhood assures dignity to all citizens and the country's unity and integrity.

India's global projection is rooted in the idea of 'unity in diversity'. India is indeed a wide collection of cultures and civilizations⁴ that attracts many across the world. The roots of soft power really move very deep. Appraisals of India's soft power is an impetus to traditional, religious, ethno-linguistic and constructive relations with other nations. The components of the Indian culture were intriguing but at the same time fascinating for the world.

India dedicated itself to contributing internationally through commerce and statecraft, apart from "soft" power. Upanishads proclaimed the idea of 'Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam' to the world and to India. Renowned ancient Indian philosopher, Chanakya's astuteness to win over adjacent powers by settlement and non-aggression arrangement and grants demonstrated the significance of soft power⁵ even in the ancient Indian statecraft.

India that has given birth to several academicians, intellectuals and scholars who have committed to the conception of distributing the knowledge, the pearls of wisdom to the geography far exceeding the frontiers of India. The ancient universities of India were the most important centres of cultural synergy and soft power. India drew quite a number of scholars and learners from different parts of the world. This mystic civilization has interested academicians, scholars and people from various parts of the globe. Various Indologists like Hiuen Tsang and Fa Hien were enamoured by rich culture and literature of India. Indian society and culture that encompass Indian cuisines, religions, festivals, spirituality, yoga, movies and music have a more all-embracing impact on the global market, particularly in Asia, West Asia, Europe and Africa.

Effect of Colonial Rule on India's Landscape

India since ages has been witness to many conflicts beginning from the era of the ancient Indian kingdoms and despots including the colonial British rule. In spite of that, India was euphoric and proud of the passive-resistance mode in which the nation had gained independence. Prior to British coming to India, India could boast of 20% of the of the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) whereas Britain had merely 2%.Ironically in 1947 during Independence, when the British departed from India, the GDP was the other way round. India economically became a weak nation quickly after gaining freedom, completely drained of its resources by colonial powers of over a period of almost three centuries. India despite its inherent complexities of encompassing diverse ethnicities and numerous cultures was broadly admired for having gained independence from the colonial rule with largely non-violent methods.

Soft power of India has the capability to connect, strengthen the bonding and to heal the scars caused by history and politics. In the 1990s, India espoused peaceful advancement and a good friendly policy towards its neighbours and the soft power in consonance with India's foreign policy to reaching out to South Asia. Grains of soft power of India have travelled through her extensive social and civilization heritage over millennia. Her purposes of secularism, liberalism and inclusiveness of cultures are even more relevant in today's restless society. Profound commitment to express genuine solidarity with developing nations is an added dimension of Indian soft power⁶ in various parts of the globe. The Gandhian concepts of non-violence, Nehru's Five Postulates of Panchsheel (Peaceful Coexistence) and the globally acclaimed Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) during the cold war propelled it to the position of an important protagonist in international fora.

Paragon of Culture, Dialogue and Synergy

Jawaharlal Nehru, India's first Prime Minister was confident that the country was raring to claim a great and benevolent share in international affairs pie. India had an image of promoter of culture, dialogue and Synergy. The religious leader of the Tibetans, his holiness Dalai Lama proclaimed, "India's great tradition of religious tolerance can be a role model for the entire world".

National unity is the prerequisite of a strong and unified India, specifically in the days of extremism and terrorism. Mahatma Gandhi sacrificed his life for the sake of communal unity. Although, there are different communities like Tamilians, Bengalis, Maharashtrians, Gujaratis, Punjabis, etc. the facts remain that despite divisions and differences, caste or creed, Indians have lived together for thousands of years. Though, there are differences between the Hindu and the Muslim communities concerning their cultures, ideology, and rituals yet they live together and have a deep-rooted respect for each other. The Hindus extend greetings to their Muslim friends at the time of their Muslim festivals such as Eid⁷ etc. likewise, the Muslims also wish or greets their Hindu friends at the time of Hindu festivals such as Diwali, Durga puja, etc. this exhibits the spirit of unity among the Hindus and the Muslims in India.

The Zoroastrians, whose doctrines influenced the principles of Judaism and Christianity, fled from Persia, modern-day Iran to India in the 7th century to save themselves from

religious and political persecution. Over centuries, a thriving community of engineers, bankers, industrialists and traders prospered along India's west coast. Parsis vouch for the hospitality of India and its people⁸. Hundreds of years ago when their land was conquered, they were persecuted and forcibly made to renounce their religion and convert by the invaders, their forefathers chose to flee our land and go looking for asylum. Jadav Rana, a Hindu Ruler, gave them shelter and protection. Ever since then this Great land, been Parsis' home full of acceptance, love and affection.

For tens of thousands of Jewish Israeli youngsters who backpack through India after their army service, the general opinion seems to reflect being treated quite well. In fact, Jewish people are grateful that most Indians are tolerant, welcoming and indeed highly accommodating. The miniscule population of Jewish Indian citizens has always been treated well by Hindu population. Three years ago, Mark Ragev Ji the then Ambassador of Israel to the UK, while speaking on the occasion of The Festival of Bharat was quite eloquent about treatment of Jewish people in India. He said:

What needs to be emphasised is that when Jewish people lost their independence in their homeland they were scattered across the planet. Jews lived in Poland and in Holland, in India and in Morocco....In many places Jewish people suffered, faced discrimination, institutionalized discrimination. You have all heard stories of the pogroms and the Nazi holocaust....As far as I know, in India Jewish community was never prosecuted. There never was a phenomenon known as antisemitism. The treatment Jews received in India is something you (People of Indianorigin) can be proud of and there is something I am thankful for.

Economic Reforms and Incredible India

With the advent of liberalization in the Indian economy, history saw an enhanced intertwining among the nations across the world. The soft power has now been accepted as the essential component of the overall power of a nation. It can add to the adhesion and the willingness of the people in an arena and the capability to shape the foreign relations of a nation. Soft power has also become an important equipment in India's foreign policy and strategic decisions toolkit⁹.

India has been one of the most important members of UNESCO and has been a stout champion of inter-civilizational and inter-cultural exchange. Tourism campaign of Incredible India came across as a whiff of fresh air in advancing 'Brand India' and offering an attractive epithet to describe the initiative taken by India to arouse world's interest in and project India as a viable destination for investment. India could hold its own amongst the formidable players with robust pillars of soft power. The country's vibrant democracy, independent judiciary, the role of NGOs, and of course progressive and free media draw people across the world. India is also vying for global recognition of its truly remarkable innovative projects, which manifest India's outreach in the field of IT. India has a large pool of highly skilled technocrat youths who are contributing their bits in all spheres across the world.

There is no denying the fact that hard power cannot be employed exceeding a frontier or territory, it is soft power that can project India and create a métier for the country in today's

world order. Representation of soft power have also undergone a change and driven home the point that India in the modern era is as much more rapid than what it was several decades ago. Moreover, Indian diaspora is performing a tremendous role in expanding the soft power of the country through the significant positions that they hold in their adopted countries¹⁰. According to an estimate more than 20 million active Indian Diasporas are spread across the globe. United Nations (UN) has predicted that India would be becoming the world's most populous country by 2024. Indian diaspora will continue to grow which is an important robust ensemble for creating a positive perception of the nation.

Innovative Use of Soft Power

India's succeeding governments have strived to expand her soft power in diverse forms. Innovative trends in the realm of Indian diplomacy are being brought forward by the government of Narendra Modi presently at the helm of affairs, by blending contemporary elements of soft power. Today, the state is using specific soft power assets of India such as Diaspora, Yoga, Buddhism and economic support for expanding diplomatic reach and realising the nation's national interests and aspirations.

The way India's Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) is making use of "Soft power Matrix" to measure the efficacy of the country's soft power outreach¹¹ is really applaudable. MEA's challenge is going to be to draw sufficient conclusions from insufficient premises in the aforementioned regard. 'Destination India' and 'Know India' initiatives have been launched by MEA arousing substantial interest and curiosity. Cultural centres like the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) conducted a national convention 'Destination India' initiative for the first time in 2019. ICCR has the believes that India can fast become a major contributor in enhancing the global knowledge by working as valuable member of the Global Knowledge Society. 'Namaste diplomacy' and 'Medical diplomacy' of India today has become buzzwords post-COVID-19.

India's achievements in the realm of space and technology are added principally induced soft power means with significant prospects. India's diplomacy has attained outer space dimension with the nation launching its GSAT-9, also known as the South Asia Satellite. This space capsule aims to bestow space-enabled services upon South Asian countries.

Constraints of India's Soft Power

Although India is a country rich in soft power resources but she lacks an institutional ecosystem to harness soft power¹² and further its national interests in the international sphere. There have been impediments due to major quandaries such as corruption, poverty, and violence against women, hostility to business, pollution in urban areas, caste-discrimination and gender-inequality that has made India fare rather badly in the coliseum of national attraction.

There are numerous factors at play decreasing the effectiveness of performance in the Soft Power 30 index for India such as the western bias that places India at a relative disadvantage as advanced economy nations take a lead. The index is a composite pattern amalgamating data across different ranges of soft power metrics to create a unique score for every nation. Subdued

performance in various sub-indices of the report hauls down a nation's overall score. However, it doesn't mean such a country will not have formidable might and valuable instruments in its display of soft power assets.

India should analyse its strengths if it wants to resurrect its national image. Its ancient wisdom and spirituality may become a key factor in exhorting other nations to acknowledge that India can have a great stewardship role in the world. India's ability to tell a "better story" has not exactly been utilised to the fullest extent in coming up with notably desired outcomes. The nation's potential of soft power if arrayed, definitely would complement India's exalted position, in making it gracious and composed power¹³ in the world. In the mounting multipolar global order, India definitely has the potential and capability. She holds immense opportunities to elevate its position further as the 'Rising global soft power' that can ultimately pave way for the country to become a 'soft power-superpower' of the 21st century.

India is a land of endearing heritage and has been an amazing kaleidoscope of the trials, tribulations and evolution. Furthermore, it has maintained an engaging traditional society and yet at the same time managed finding its feet to the global popular culture. Influence of the soft power of India at the world stage was a great ingress. India has been considered a melting pot of cultures, beliefs and languages¹⁴. She has showcased herself as a novel civilization by embracing a clearly unambiguous and tolerant use of constructing its civilization. India is opulently enriched with unique flora and fauna, and is an active cultural-anthropological gallery. Traditional and age-old, characterisation of the Hindu faith as an understanding and pluralistic system has enabled India to define itself as a non-violent and magnanimous society. India as a nation has had abundantly more to contribute in courses of its connections with other parts of the world.

India has been granting shelter, religious and cultural freedom to Jews, Christians, Muslims and several other faiths since the time immemorial. India's history and culture is her heritage to the world that exhibits the metamorphosis of India's narrative. How India seamlessly and harmoniously assimilated different religions yet never lost track to its own culture and history is indeed an inspiring story.

Harvard professor Joseph Nye at the outset, introduced the notion of soft power in 1990. He described it as "a dynamic created by a nation whereby other nations seek to emulate that nation, become closer to that nation, and align its interest accordingly". A nation's soft power, according to Nye depends on three resources: "its culture, its political values, and its foreign policies".

Connections with Latin America and Caribbean Region

Tryst of India's soft power with Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) nations dates back to the pre-independence era. It has only got more strengthened in the contemporary world. Indian Ayurveda, classical dances and cuisines, history, literature, movies, philosophy, yoga, are well known in the LAC region. These Indian attributes are manifesting Indian soft power in the region like never before. India's cultural appeal in the LAC nations is a robust instrument of India's soft power¹⁵ in the region. LAC contains abundant deposits of natural resources and is

a big continent with a vibrant population. India's soft power resources project a positive image of India in the LAC nations that assist India to boost its political and economic relations with LAC countries. It gives India an inestimable source of raw materials for its industries and is an outstanding market for its products. Being one of the most extensive exporters of agriculture products, LAC nations can play a pivotal function in facilitating India to achieve food security and energy.

India, historically, could not pay much attention to the nations in the LAC due to India's engrossment with the other countries and the apprehensions of the country's businessmen, economic policymakers and export organizations to make considerable investments to cater for new markets. Traditionally, The LAC nations maintained most of their political and economic engagement with Europe and the U.S. India's empathetic understanding of Latin America with staggering external debt and India's introvert economic approach precluded it from establishing trade relations with LAC. Moreover, topographical range, language and communication also posed barriers. India's soft power in Latin America gradually began being more pronounced in the post-independence period. Post-Cold War and India's Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization (LPG) reforms, there was liberalisation of economies of India and LAC, that presented an opportunity for the two sides to expand their mutual political and economic relations.

Initial Spell of Indian Soft Power in LAC Region

Very initial Indian soft power conjuration in Latin America was through the literature works of famous Bengali writer and poet Nobel Laureate Rabindranath Tagore. The works of literature of Tagore influenced two prominent Chilean poets, Gabriela Mistral and Pablo Neruda who eventually became the Nobel Laureates. Even, today Tagore's literature continues to be read in Latin American academies. Indian classical dances have also become very sought after in LAC. A large number of Latin Americans are displaying penchant in Indian traditional dances. Similarly, the Indian film industry's (Bollywood) association with LAC goes back to the 1970s when movies like "Mother India and Mera Naam Joker" were released. These movies ran to full houses to become huge hits. Bollywood indeed has a huge fan following in many LAC nations¹⁶. Indian cuisines being one of the most popular cuisines in the world has also been receiving significant traction in Latin America. Indian restaurants are popular in many LAC nations.

Aspects of Indian Soft Appeal in LAC Region

Yoga is now embraced in LAC as a way to achieve good fitness and mental well-being. Quite a number of yoga centres are open across LAC with Brazil boasting of having the highest number of centres is in Brazil. In the area of Ayurveda, India is conducting conclaves and seminars in different LAC nations to promote awareness about this holistic health system. Brazil runs an Ayurvedic foundation called Associacao Brasileira de Ayurveda (ABRA) to support Ayurveda in Brazil. Knowledge of Ayurveda has been proliferated by the Fundacion Salud de Ayurved Prema Argentina throughout Latin America spanning more than 20 years. The Fundacion is based in Buenos Aires in the Argentine Republic, where it now runs courses

in two of the country's major medical schools - at the School of Medicine of the University of Buenos Aires, and the National University of Cordoba's School of Medicine. The Fundacion has been accredited as a Collaborating Centre for teaching, assistance and research in the field of Ayurvedic Medicine in Argentina supported by a MoU with Gujarat Ayurveda University, at Jamnagar¹⁷, Gujarat. This has led to successful missions to other countries in the region where the Fundacion and its associates have been able to start dialogues with governments, and in places hold sizeable courses. The knowledge of Ayurveda is now spreading throughout South and Central America and hardly a country remains untouched by it.

There is also a huge following of Indian institutions, foundations and spiritual leaders in LAC. Many Indian cultural centres have proliferated in the LAC nations. The biggest and most prominent amongst them is ISKCON (International Society for Krishna Consciousness), which is also known as 'Hare Krishna Movement'. The largest and the most prominent ISKCON Centre in LAC region is situated in Brazil, which was instituted in the 1970s. ISKCON has centres in the majority of the LAC nations including Panama, Dominican Republic, Costa Rica, El Salvador and West Indies. In the same vein, The Art of Living foundation has massive followers in LAC where, Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, its founder is immensely popular. His reputation in the region also helped in fostering peace and harmony between the Colombian government and the FARC (Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia) guerrillas.

India's soft power in LAC has been witnessing a gradual surge. The Caribbean nations no doubt are huge soft power assets for India. The Indian Diaspora are proud of their Indian heritage and are keen to learn more about India¹⁸, its past and present and they keep Indian culture alive and vibrant in the region as per reports of India's Ministry of External Affairs (MEA). Besides, there is also a large Indian diaspora in Suriname, Jamaica, Guyana, and Trinidad and Tobago, which is further espousing Indian cultures, and tradition that is celebrated in these countries. Government of India, Indian cultural centres and its embassies in the LAC require to enhance India's soft power. They should host more cultural celebrations and further provide scholarships to the LAC students to study in Indian academies, universities and strengthen student exchange programmes where the students can explore the cultures and values of India and bring about a positive image of India in LAC nations. The Indian foreign policy also requires to be refurbished to give escalated importance to the LAC nations.

CONCLUSION

LAC nations are important for India as these nations can further assist India to gain a permanent seat in the UNSC. Platforms like the Caribbean Conclave and India – Latin America business conclaves must be used to stimulate relations and extend areas of partnership and bilateral understanding. India can engross LAC nations through various other fora such as BRICS, Commonwealth and NAM also. The media should likewise play a positive role in strengthening India's soft power as the LAC nations have largely been ignored in the Indian popular media.

LAC nations provide plethora of opportunities that have hitherto remained considerably untapped. India should take active interest and strive to expand its soft appeal footprints in the LAC region.

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